

POLYMER-IMPREGNATED BUCKYPAPER AS STRUCTURAL MATERIAL FOR MICROACTUATORS

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SUMMARY

Carbon nanotube-reinforced polymer composites are promising structural materials for microactuators as they can offer actuation speeds comparable to traditional ceramics and metals at considerably lower actuation voltages. This fact is experimentally demonstrated through the fabrication and characterization of polymer-impregnated buckypaper thin films.

Keywords: Nanotubes, Nanocomposites, Buckypaper, Resin Infiltration, MEMS

1. INTRODUCTION

Microactuators are common elements of microelectromechanical systems (MEMS). To fulfill actuation speed requirements, ceramics and metals are traditionally used as structural materials for microactuators due to their high longitudinal wave velocity ($\sqrt{E/\rho}$) in which E and ρ are Young's modulus and mass density, respectively. However, the required energy for their activation is significantly higher than polymer microactuators due to their higher stiffness. It has been theoretically demonstrated that polymer composites can offer better performance by decreasing the actuation voltages and achieving speeds comparable to metals and ceramics [1]. Carbon nanotubes (CNT) are potentially promising as polymer reinforcing elements for this application due to their appropriate sizes and properties. The direct addition of CNT to polymers, however, significantly increases the viscosity of the resin, resulting in various challenges to manufacture composite microactuators through traditional techniques. Moreover, direct mixing techniques result in low percentages of CNT inside polymers (typically less than 1% by weight), not enough for the required property improvements. Alternatively, CNT sheets, also called buckypaper (BP), have potential for this application due to their high volume fractions of CNT (25 to 40% by volume) and the relative ease of fabrication to varying thickness from the submicron level to hundreds of micrometers. However, due to weak interactions between CNT, the overall Young's modulus of BP is relatively low (1-5 GPa) as compared with CNT themselves (~1 TPa). As a result, the polymer impregnation of BP is a necessary step to improve performance. In this work, a combination of theoretical and experimental techniques is used to investigate the possibility of using BP to manufacture microactuators.

2. MICROACTUATORS

Microactuators are common elements of microelectromechanical systems (MEMS). The actuation of micromachined structural components is achieved primarily by using electrostatic forces [2]. Electrostatically-actuated MEMS are used for a wide range of applications including displays (e.g., Digital Mirror Displays commercialized by Texas Instruments), and electromechanical switches and oscillators [3]. A representative geometry for an electrostatic actuator is a microbeam of constant rectangular cross section, as shown in Figure. 1. The structural dimensions range from hundreds of nanometers to tens of micrometers. This structure is actuated by applying an electrostatic potential difference between the beam and the substrate.

Figure 1: Schematic illustration of an electrostatically actuated microbeam.

The performance metrics for electrostatic actuators are the actuation voltage, which is proportional to the stiffness of the structure [2], and the speed of actuation, which is proportional to the frequency of vibrations [2]. A common requirement in many applications is to design high-speed, low-voltage actuators [4]. Hence, there is great interest in optimizing geometry and material properties to achieve these goals.

The selection of materials for isotropic, homogeneous and monolithic beam structures has been addressed previously [4]. The stiffness of the beam can be expressed as [5]:

$$k = \lambda_1 \frac{EI}{L^3} \quad (1)$$

where λ_1 is a constant whose value depends on the boundary conditions, E is Young's modulus, I is the area moment of inertia, and L is the beam length. Similarly, the frequency of vibrations is given by [6]:

$$f = \lambda_2 \left(\frac{h}{L^2} \right) \sqrt{\frac{E}{\rho}} \quad (2)$$

where λ_2 is a constant, h is the beam thickness, and ρ is the density. Therefore, for a specified geometry and boundary condition, the stiffness and frequency are only functions of the material indices E and $\sqrt{E/\rho}$, respectively. The ratio $\sqrt{E/\rho}$ is also the constituent wave velocity for an isotropic solid, represented by c . As the first step in

materials selection, the approach of Ashby [5, 6] can be used. Figure 2 shows a graph of longitudinal wave velocity as a function of Young's modulus. This figure indicates that ceramics (e.g., diamond, silicon carbide, silicon nitride and silicon) and metals (e.g., aluminum and nickel) exhibit high values of both Young's modulus and $\sqrt{E/\rho}$. These materials are now widely used to fabricate high-speed actuators [2, 4], but the increase in speed is achieved at the expense of relatively high actuation voltages. An alternate choice of materials is suggested by Figure 2. Some polymer composites (typically fiber-reinforced structures) have high wave velocity but lower stiffness. Thus, the use of these materials can potentially lead to a reduction of the actuation voltage at speeds comparable to typical metals and ceramics.

A limited amount of work on microfabrication using nanowire and nanotube composites has been reported. A prototype of a nanocomposite thermoelectric microdevice was designed and fabricated by Abramson *et al.* [7] where an array of silicon nanowires was embedded within a parylene polymer. A nanocomposite electrothermal microactuator was manufactured by using electroless deposition of a mixture of nickel and multi-walled carbon nanotubes [8]. The Young's modulus of the nanocomposite film reinforced with a nanotube volume fraction of 28% was reported to be higher by a factor of four versus pure nickel [8].

Figure 2: Wave velocity versus Young's modulus for different classes of materials.

3. MICROMECHANICS OF SHORT-FIBRE COMPOSITES

In this section, a modelling approach based on micromechanics was used to evaluate the suitability of buckypaper as structural material for microactuators. The continuum model based on the method of Mori and Tanaka is the most powerful micromechanics technique for elastic characterization of short-fibre composites (in this case carbon nanotubes) [9] and is capable of addressing the following characteristics of short-fibre composites:

- 1) The geometry, i.e. aspect ratio, of the fibres or inclusions
- 2) The volume fraction of the inclusions

- 3) The alignment or orientation of the inclusions (considered to be three dimensionally random for CNT within buckypaper composites)
- 4) The elastic properties of matrix and fibre (for both isotropic and anisotropic properties)

All these issues are important for CNT composites. It is assumed that the interfacial properties are optimized to give a perfect load transfer between fibres and matrix. In that sense, the analysis will lead to an upper bound on the elastic properties.

The effective stiffness tensor of the composite (C^C) is defined as

$$\bar{\sigma} = C^C \bar{\epsilon} \quad (3)$$

where $\bar{\sigma}$ and $\bar{\epsilon}$ are, respectively, the averaged stress and the averaged strain of the composite. It has been shown that this stiffness tensor can be obtained through the following equation [10]:

$$C^C = C^M + V_f \langle (C^I - C^M) A \rangle \quad (4)$$

where C^C and C^M are the stiffness tensors of the inclusions and the matrix, respectively. V_f is the volume fraction of inclusions, and the angular brackets denote the averaged quantity over all orientations. A is the concentration factor. For a dilute composite in which the interaction between inclusions can be neglected A is defined as:

$$A^{dil} = \left[I + S(C^M)^{-1}(C^I - C^M) \right]^{-1} \quad (5)$$

where S is the Eshelby Tensor and is a function of the nanotube aspect ratio and the Poisson's ratio of the matrix and its elements can be found elsewhere [1, 11]. For the case of high concentrations of inclusions within short-fibre composites interaction between inclusions can not be neglected. As a result, Mori and Tanaka [12] suggested an energy approach to include this effect. Based on this approach, Benveniste [13] presented a close-form solution to calculate the concentration factor for a non-dilute composite:

$$A^{non-dil} = A^{dil} \left[(1 - V_f) I + V_f \langle A^{dil} \rangle \right]^{-1} \quad (6)$$

Figure 3 shows the modulus and longitudinal wave velocity of polymer-impregnated buckypaper as a function of CNT volume fraction. Bundles or arrays of CNT were assumed to have Young's modulus, aspect ratio and density of 580 GPa, 1000 and 1.3 g/cm³, respectively. A representative polymer matrix with Young's modulus and density of 3 GPa and 1.2 g/cm³, respectively, was assumed. As mentioned previously, 3D random distribution of CNT was assumed within the nanocomposite. According to the literature, a range from 10 to 50% was also assumed for the nanotube volume fraction [14]. As can be seen in Figure 3, a CNT volume fraction of 30% results in a considerable increase of wave velocity (5800 m/s) as compared with the pure polymer

(1700 m/s) while the Young's modulus (50 GPa) is still below those of most metals and some ceramics (for example for Ni, $E=180$ GPa and $c=4500$).

Figure 3: Wave velocity and Young's modulus of polymer-impregnated buckypaper as a function of carbon nanotube volume fraction.

4. NANOCOMPOSITE MANUFACTURING

4.1 Preparation of buckypaper sheets

Buckypaper used in this work was manufactured at National Research Council Canada Steacie Institute for Molecular Sciences (NRC-SIMS) using laser-generated single-walled carbon nanotubes (SWCNT) produced at the same institute. Details of SWCNT manufacturing and purification can be found in the literature [15,16]. These films have thicknesses varying from 50 to 70 μm , areas of approximately 10 cm^2 , void contents of 65-75% by volume and an impurity content of around 10% by weight. SWCNT are first dispersed in Tetrahydrofuran (THF) and then diluted with ethanol. After sonication, the solution was filtered through a polycarbonate membrane with a pore size of 20 μm under low vacuum of a water pump. The wet buckypaper with the membrane was kept under compression overnight until it was partially dried. After separation of buckypaper from the membrane, it was completely dried in an oven at 85°C.

4.2 Impregnation of buckypaper

Buckypaper films were impregnated through the thickness with a two component aerospace-grade epoxy resin (Araldite® MY0510 and 4,4-Diaminodiphenyl Sulphone hardener) using vacuum infiltration. An appropriate amount of resin calculated based on the void content was placed on the buckypaper. A schematic of the infiltration setup is shown in Figure 4. Full vacuum was applied to the bottom of the buckypaper using a thin layer of breather cloth with a perforated Teflon layer inserted between buckypaper and breather cloth to facilitate the separation of nanocomposite after impregnation. The epoxy resin has a viscosity of 10 Pa.s at room temperature and 0.1 Pa.s at 100°C. The impregnation process was optimized so that a 100°C infusion temperature was used at

which the resin maintains minimum viscosity. A thin layer of tacky tape was used to prevent the resin from escaping at the edges of the buckypaper.

Figure 4: Schematic illustration of the vacuum infiltration technique of buckypaper.

5. NANOCOMPOSITE CHARACTERIZATION

A Hitachi S-4700 Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) was used for qualitative evaluation of pristine buckypaper sheet and produced nanocomposites. Other characterization techniques are explained in the following sections:

5.1 Density and Void Measurements

The density of pristine buckypaper sheets was estimated through area, thickness, and weight measurements. To estimate the void content of buckypaper, a density of 1.15 g/cm^3 was assumed for nanotube arrays assuming an average diameter of 0.9 nm for SWCNT produced with the laser technique. In order to evaluate the resin content of impregnated buckypaper, thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) was performed on nanocomposite samples using a Netzsch TG 209 F1 Iris® TGA under an inert gas (argon) to burn off only the resin. Tests were carried out from room temperature to 600°C with a heating rate of $10^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$. Results from resin content measurements were later used to evaluate void content of impregnated buckypaper sheets.

5.2 Modulus Calculations

The mechanical properties of thin films can be measured using the bending of a circular composite plate clamped at its edge. Figure 5 shows a custom-made testing jig that is installed on a Hysitron Triboindenter to perform these tests. This instrument is capable of measuring loads and displacement with resolutions of a few μN and nm respectively. In addition, the Triboindenter is equipped with an optical system to specify the point of load application accurately. The load-deflection curves obtained from the bending test, combined with a mechanical model for the bending deformation, are used to determine the Young's modulus of the specimen. From Timoshenko's plate theory [17] the elastic Young's modulus of a clamped circular plate of radius a and thickness h is given by:

$$E = \frac{3(1-\nu^2)}{4\pi} \frac{a^2}{h^3} \frac{P}{\delta_r - \delta_c} \quad (7)$$

where P and δ are the load and deflection at the centre of the circular plate, respectively, and ν is the Poisson's ratio of the film. The main advantage of this technique is the ability to characterize thin films with lateral dimensions of only 3 to 4 mm and thicknesses of a few tens of micrometers.

Figure 5: A schematic illustration of the loading fixture used to measure modulus.

6. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Fig. 6 shows cross sectional SEM images of buckypaper sheets before and after impregnation, demonstrating the successful manufacture of epoxy/buckypaper (nanocomposite) thin films. The presence of small voids is also clear in the images of impregnated buckypaper proving that the impregnation is not complete (Figure 6-d). The image with a higher magnification demonstrates the presence of impurities inside pristine buckypaper (Figure 6-b). Good wetting of carbon nanotube can be clearly observed from the SEM images of impregnated specimens (Figure 6-c and -d).

Figure 7 shows the weight reduction for three thin films of pristine buckypaper, pure epoxy and impregnated buckypaper as function of temperature obtained through TGA. The weight difference between impregnated and non- impregnated specimens can be attributed to the resin content of nanocomposite films. Table 1 summarizes Young's modulus and wave velocity for four buckypaper sheets and their composites. An average void content of 69% has been estimated for the pristine buckypaper sheet. After impregnation, the average void content is reduced to 15%. Also, the average wave velocity and Young's modulus are increase from 1000 m/s and 0.5 GPa for the case of pristine buckypaper to 3200 m/s and 10.9 GPa for impregnated buckypaper sheets. Relatively large standard deviations for elastic modulus and wave velocity can be attributed to the non-uniform infiltration of nanocomposite. The overall elastic modulus of nanocomposite thin films was increased by factors of 3.5 and 22 when compared with the pure epoxy films and neat buckypaper films, respectively.

Figure 6: Cross-sectional view of pristine (*a* and *b*) and impregnated buckypaper (*c* and *d*) sheets taken by scanning electron microscope.

Figure 7: Weight reduction of buckypaper, nanocomposite and epoxy film as function of temperature during TGA tests.

Figure 8 shows wave velocity as a function of Young's modulus for different classes of materials. A best result from buckypaper composites provides a speed (wave velocity) comparable to typical metals (Al, Ni) at a significantly lower actuation voltage (or E). This graph also shows predictions using Mori-Tanaka theory for an optimum case in which the nanotubes are aligned along the length of microstructures. Theoretical predictions through micromechanics suggest the possibility of a higher performance upon improvements in nanocomposite manufacturing techniques. Red dots in Figure 8 are from other experimental work found in the literature [18].

Table 1: Young's modulus and wave velocity of four different pristine buckypaper sheets and their nanocomposites

Sample	Pristine Buckypaper				Impregnated Buckypaper			
	Void (%)	ρ (g/cm ³)	E (GPa)	c (m/s)	Void (%)	ρ (g/cm ³)	E (GPa)	c (m/s)
1	70	0.46	0.58	1123	18	1.01	15.4	4070
2	65	0.48	0.74	1242	5	1.18	6.4	2370
3	65	0.49	0.40	904	5	1.18	14.5	3570
4	75	0.55	0.30	739	30	0.87	7.3	2910
Average	69±5	0.5±0.04	0.5±0.2	1000±220	15±12	1.1±0.15	10.9±4.7	3220±740

Figure 8: Wave velocity versus Young's modulus. Impregnated buckypaper has a velocity comparable to metals (Al and Ni) at significantly lower modulus (red dots are from other experimental work found in the literature).

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8. REFERENCES

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